

(Re)Use of Open Research Data: Challenges and Opportunities

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Landscape analysis

Training on data reuse

The ROAD project at the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW) aims to explore the reusability of quantitative datasets from various disciplines for student master theses by encouraging lecturers and researchers to use their datasets as sources. Challenges such as inadequate documentation, legal and ethical ambiguities, and technical competencies in software and data search were identified. So far, the project's outputs include a presentation summarizing insights (source: <https://zenodo.org/records/14245966>) and a checklist with minimum criteria for reusability which is used by both lecturers and students (source: <https://zenodo.org/records/11385459>).

Looking ahead, extending these efforts to reuse published datasets could significantly benefit the scientific community, potentially leading to additional training activities for early-career researchers or collaborations, and establishing data reuse as a commonly accepted good practice in conducting research.

As of June 2025, the initial ROADS project was concluded and shall be continued with a follow-up project ROADS-2 starting in January 2026.

Funding of projects reusing data

Funding tends to focus on innovative research, there is a strong emphasis on novelty in research. Therefore, reusing existing research data may be seen as less innovative, even if it contributes to reproducibility and validation of findings. Sharing our experiences, the authors outlined opportunities of funding and use cases where such research was supported.

- In the Netherlands, the ZonMw had a grant call recently to conduct research with existing data ([source](#)).
- FAIR-IMPACT provides an overview of use cases of FAIR Data Curation, not limited to FAIR Data Reuse ([source](#))
- The NIH has an open call competitive revision applications that focus on data reuse and secondary data analysis in NIH-funded data repositories ([source](#))
- Data re-use awards from the Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences (FORS) ([source](#))

In addition, there are calls that although not exclusively addressing data reuse, they are partially encouraging data sharing efforts in collaborative, translational settings. For example, the SNSF and EU joint program Neurodegenerative Disease Research (JPND) launched in 2024 a transnational call on mechanisms and measurement of disease progression in the early phase of neurodegenerative diseases ([source](#)).

Due to the limitation on time during the Open Science Retreat, the authors welcome any and all other opportunities and use-cases to strengthen the support for conducting research with existing (Open) Research Data.

Use cases of projects reusing data

There are abundant resources on making data reusable and making data FAIR. The site FAIR-Impact (<https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases>) “identifies practices, policies, tools and technical specifications to guide researchers, repository managers, research performing organisations, policy makers and citizen scientists towards a FAIR data management cycle” (see also the [booklet](#) summarizing use cases). However, here we are interested in the next step, that is, on finding use cases of successful data reuse.

- OpenAIRE collects stories and use cases reporting the process and experiences of data reuse (Source: <https://www.openaire.eu/data-reuse-use-cases>). This is developed by the RDM Task Force - Data Reuse Working Group.
- This presentation from the Cambridge Data Week 2020 analyses present and future trends of reusing data <https://unlockingresearch-blog.lib.cam.ac.uk/?p=2911>

Some field-specific communities also provide success stories of data reuse. For example:

- The BonaRes repository for SOil research gathers some success stories on data reuse. <https://www.bonares.de/news/success-stories-on-data-reuse>. They also provide [a template](#) for researchers that want to share their story.
- An article from the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EBML, source: <https://www.embl.org/news/people-perspectives/data-standards-impact/>) points at a highly influential case of data reuse in the field. The article also describes the concept of *minimal information standards* to “strike a balance between what is possible and what is practical”.
- The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD) provides a list of case studies of data reuse (source: <https://www.i-hd.eu/knowledge-center/case-studies/>)

There are also some peer-review publications describing data reuse processes:

- Fu, J., Li, K., Zhang, W., Wan, C., Zhang, J., Jiang, P., & Liu, X. S. (2020). Large-scale public data reuse to model immunotherapy response and resistance. *Genome medicine*, 12, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-020-0721-z>
- Papoutsoglou, E. A., Athanasiadis, I. N., Visser, R. G., & Finkers, R. (2023). The benefits and struggles of FAIR data: the case of reusing plant phenotyping data. *Scientific Data*, 10(1), 457. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02364-z>

Future directions

At the Open Science Retreat 2025, discussions focused on the hurdles faced in the re-utilisation of existing research data (focusing in Switzerland and the Netherlands). Identifying the essential role that data stewards play in enabling collected data for re-use (i.e. researchers starting their data collection to make it FAIR) and utilising existing data for replication studies (i.e. disseminating good use cases of FAIR data to be used in research). However, with limited time and resources, data stewards are stretched to provide support to all researchers and FAIRify existing data in their collections.

To support the endeavours of data stewards, institutional and funding support is needed to reward and incentivise research that utilizes existing research data and promote FAIR practices in new data being collected for future research. One opportunity to facilitate this call is to support interdisciplinary research projects, where different disciplines and stakeholders are engaged to address societal questions. By working across research disciplines, ensuring that research outputs are accessible and understandable to a broader audience (i.e. policy makers, industrial partners, general public) reinforces the need to make data (re)usable across different fields.

As a follow-up action, the authors of this document will work to pilot cross-border collaboration on the re-use of existing Open Research Data